

D5.2 AMON identity and website

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No 101101521

June 2023

D5.2 AMON identity and website

Project Acronym	AMON
Project Title	Development of a next generation AMmONia FC system.
Type	HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
Project Coordinator	Matteo Testi (FBK)
Project Duration	January 1, 2023 – December 31, 2025 (36 Months)
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Table of Contents

01. Introduction	3
02. Visual Identity	4
03. Branding Guidelines	9
04. Communication materials	13
05. Project Website and Socials	14
06. Conclusions	18

List of Figures

Figure 1. AMON Logo	5
Figure 2. AMON Pictogram	5
Figure 3. AMON Colour palette	5
Figure 4. AMON Typography	6
Figure 5. AMON Template for Power Point Presentation	7
Figure 6 AMON Template for Word documents.....	8
Figure 7. Screenshot of AMON Branding Guidelines	12
Figure 8. Screenshot of the AMON repository.....	13
Figure 9. AMON website - "Project"	14
Figure 10. Consortium webpage	15
Figure 11. AMON website - "Prototype"	15
Figure 12. AMON Website "Results"	16
Figure 13. AMON Website "News"	16
Figure 14. Screenshot of the social media account of AMON project.....	17

01. Introduction

This deliverable describes the work performed within the Task 5.2 of the AMON project in the first six months.

Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) oversees the Communication activities and in January 2023 started the administrative procedure to find a contractor that would support the team in designing the visual identity of the project, the communication materials, and the website. All Partners have been involved in decision on the design, the content and other details such as the colors to be included.

This activity is considered an important part of the project as the materials are defining the identity of the project, how the project will transmit a feeling on the different contents at the technological, scientific, and market levels.

Furthermore, the visual identity, the logo and the communication materials will be the building blocks of the present and future dissemination and communication (D&C) activities and will characterise the project as a distinguishable brand.

The website will be the main communication channel of the project and it will be periodically updated. It will be used to share information, news on the status of the activities, and public results and knowledge developed in AMON. It is the key platform for sharing open-source publications, public deliverables, conference proceedings and presentations that will be published by the partners.

The visual identity and the website are functional to the D&C strategy that will be detailed in Deliverable D5.3 "Dissemination and Communication Plan" scheduled by June 2023 (EFCF), which will maximize the dissemination and communication potential of the project.

The document is structured in three main sections. The first section describes the conceptualisation of the visual identity, including the logo, the colour palette, and the pay-off. The second section presents the branding guidelines. Then, the D&C materials for conferences, workshops and other events are presented. Finally, the last section outlines the website structure and functionalities.

02. Visual Identity

Paul Rand was an American graphic designer well known for having created the logos of world leading corporations. He was quoted as having said that “*Design is the silent ambassador of your brand*”. In fact, the visual identity is the element that makes a brand immediately identifiable by users and customers.

This is the reason why visual identity plays such a significant role European project as well. The EU Commission asks the beneficiaries to “promote the action and its results [...] in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”. The first step is to make sure that the stakeholders the project wishes to engage with have clearly understood who their interlocutor is.

Visual identity presents the project to internal and external stakeholders, it tells a story through the visual communications. The visual identity captures and expresses the values and ambitions of the project, the core activities, and its characteristics. It includes a logo, imagery, typography, colours, and creative design that characterize a project as a distinguishable brand.

The visual identity of the project AMON has been developed in collaboration with the subcontractor “Comunicazione e Design (eDesign)”. The subcontractor helped the WP5 team and the coordinator in extracting the core concepts of the project, the main symbols, and the key messages to be conveyed through the visual identity.

The team went through several stages and discussions to consider the alternative ideas and select the most effective identity for the project PROMETEO. First of all, a meeting between the coordinator and the subcontractor was scheduled in order to make the communication agency understand what the project was about. Then, the subcontractor started building the logo, colours, and typography. Five proposals were sent. Most of the partners decided the one described in section 2.1.

Then, the focus was pointed to 3D images. These initially focused on the applications of the technology rather than the AMON system itself. Consequently, the focus was switched to the technology and specific components. Exchanges Partners were always carried during the conceptualisation, but their involvement was fundamental at the moment of the graphic creation of the technology.

In the next sections, each part of the visual identity is described.

2.1 Logo

The logo makes the first impression.

Initially, it is the first think that attract the attention of users and audience and might spark their interests. Then, it is easy to reproduce. It not only helps differentiating AMON from other projects with similar names, but it strengthens the message that the project as in a unique word and graphic symbol the logo embeds the main concepts and meanings of the project.

The creation of the project stated with the identification of the basic, core concepts. The project AMON aim to develop a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell system. From this description, two key concepts of AMON have been identified, summarized and drawn: the logo is characterized by the NH₃ molecule that locates itself on the final part of the lettering. Another strong element is the symbol of the ignition "ON" which, as integral part of the name, emphasizes the narrative "from ammonia to power".

Figure 1. AMON Logo

The concept is strengthened with the pictogram, which only reports the symbol of the ignition "ON" and the NH₃ molecule.

Figure 2. AMON Pictogram

Besides the shape, colours are another distinguishing feature of a brand identity. The blue colour represents water and atmosphere, while green represents earth, chemical reaction and green energy. "Green" was considered a fundamental colour for communicating the ambition of the project to address the clean energy transition, using green ammonia to create green hydrogen.

Figure 3. AMON Colour palette

The other characterizing element of a logo is the payoff. The payoff is defined as a short and striking phrase used to better define the logo and to clarify the identity of the project. It has the attributes of being memorable, very concise and appealing to the audience. The sentence is “Ammonia to Power”.

It is always used with the logo and appears in Figure 1. “Ammonia” describes the basis of the project, “Power” identifies the target and result.

After having selected the design, colours and payoff, the final element to conclude the logo is the font. The font selected for AMON is “Google Font Dosis” a rounded sans-serif type family. The font can be downloaded at <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Dosis>.

As supporting font for the pay-off and for longer texts, the font selected was “Google Font Rubik”, another sans serif font family with slightly rounded corners. The font can be downloaded at <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Rubik>

Figure 4. AMON Typography

The final logo is a combination of design, colour, font and sentence which will be used for all the communication and dissemination material of the project.

2.2 Template

The visual identity of AMON has been used to design the template for Power Point presentations (Figure 5), and for Word document (Figure 6).

Figure 5. AMON Template for Power Point Presentation

The templates report the logo of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership alongside the EU flag and the acknowledgement, which cites *"The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No 101101521"*. The templates are important elements of the visual identity since they help to characterize the project AMON as brand in presentations and other external D&C activities, as well as in public documents. Templates have been made available to project partners through the project repository on SharePoint: [Documents > General > 6_Templates and logos > 03 Template](#)

FBK - Fondazione Bruno Kessler - Italy

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No. 101012141

[\(press icon\)](#)

DXX TITLE

Project Acronym	AMON
Project Title	Development of a next generation Ammonia FC system
Type	HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
Project Coordinator	Matteo Tagli (FBK)
Project Duration	January 1, 2023 - December 31, 2025 (36 Months)
Deliverable No.	DX-X
Dissemination Level	PU/SEN
Work Package	WPx - title
Task	TX - title
Lead beneficiary	T (FBK) / 2 (SEI) / 3 (VITI) / 4 (DTU) / 5 (KWA NL) / 6 (KWA IT) / 7 (ALSW) / 8 (ALDO) / 9 (ALIT) / 10 (SAPIO) / 11 (EPFL) / 12 (EPFC) / 13 (HSLU)
Contributing beneficiary(s)	T (FBK) / 2 (SEI) / 3 (VITI) / 4 (DTU) / 5 (KWA NL) / 6 (KWA IT) / 7 (ALSW) / 8 (ALDO) / 9 (ALIT) / 10 (SAPIO) / 11 (EPFL) / 12 (EPFC) / 13 (HSLU)
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Table of Contents

- 01 Introduction 3
- 02 Table A 5
- 03 Table B 6
- 04 Icons and data 7
- 05 Infographic 8
- 06 Table C 9
- 08 Ammon 10

01 Introduction

The kick-off meeting of the project AMON "Development of a next generation Ammonia FC system" was held on 29 January 2023 in Trento, hosted by Fondazione Bruno Kessler, and followed by a visit to the manufacturing site of Solid Oxide Technology by Sulystria in Pergine. All Partners were present to launch the activities of this Horizon Europe project, which will last for 3 years and is funded from the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The overarching objective of AMON project is to develop a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell system. The project will deal with the design of the basic components of the system including the fuel cell, an ammonia burner, ammonia resistant heat exchangers, the engineering of the whole balance of plants, and validation of the compliance with ammonia use for all the specific parts and components. Customarily, depending on system needs, an ammonia cracker and waste gas recirculation will be developed. The outputs of the questionnaire analysis are:

- Point 01:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.
- Point 02:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.
- Point 03:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

01 Amon

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More info:
<https://www.fbk.eu/press-releases/direct-use-of-ammonia-in-fuel-cells/>

ONLINE (LOCKED):
<https://ammonia.eu/>

02 Table A

The Smart Abilidae Questionnaire used to collect data from the soil results is divided in 7 sections. The structure is shown below:

SECTION	SUBSECTION	DESCRIPTION
01 TITLE	Sub-01a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-01b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-01c	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-01d	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
02 TITLE	Sub-02a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-02b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-02c	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-02d	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
03 TITLE	Sub-03a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-03b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-03c	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-03d	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
04 TITLE	Sub-04a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-04b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-04c	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-04d	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

03. Icons and data

	999 Kw/h Power	99 Kw * of power flow	1 * of SOFC
	100 km ² Area	10 * of SOFC	10 * of Burners
	10 Boats per day	999 l Ammonia	100% Renewable energy
	20 Sites per boat	999 l Ammonia	100% Renewable energy

05. Infographic

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

08 Ammon

Ammon - Ammonia to power

Coordinator Contacts:
 Matteo **Tagli** (mailto:tagli@fbk.eu) | FBK
 Center for Sustainable Energy | FBK

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Ammon - Ammonia to power

Coordinator Contacts:
 Matteo **Tagli** (mailto:tagli@fbk.eu) | FBK
 Center for Sustainable Energy | FBK

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No. 101012141

Figure 6 AMON Template for Word documents

03. Branding Guidelines

As initially planned and reported in the Grant Agreement, a branding book was created with the help of the subcontractor.

The document contains the rules on how to appropriately use AMON visual identity and branding elements like the logo, colours, and typography. These guidelines are relevant to ensure that all partners, but also external stakeholders, are aware of and understand the AMON identity, the concept behind it and how to make use of it in the most appropriate way.

For example, brand guidelines are a useful resource during on-boarding of new members in the project's partners, to smooth processes and to have a set of rules and standards to communicate consistently the AMON identity.

The document outlines:

- The concept description with the logo and pictogram. Logo and pictogram are in colour, white and black versions.
- The how to and the restrictions in the use the logo
- The colour palette with meaning and codes, and example of colour applications
- The logo construction lines, clearance spaces and minimum sizes to guarantee its readability.
- The typography to be used in the logo and pay-off.
- Instructions on how to acknowledge the EU Funding: The Clean Hydrogen Partnership, EU flag and acknowledgement to be included in publications, presentations, poster etc.
- Instructions on how to include the branding on infrastructures and equipment funded by AMON Project. The rules were taken from the Visual Identity Manual¹ of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The document also reports:

- Sample images that can be used with the AMON logo on it. The images have been taken from free stock of photos.
- 3D images of the technology and its applications, which have been elaborated by the subcontractor and are part of AMON Visual identity.
- Example of infographics.
- Example of applications of the visual identity: on the roll-up, on caps and flyers.
- The string of partners logos with the Clean Hydrogen acknowledgement.
- Templates of the PowerPoint presentation and Word document created.

The guidelines indicate the link where to download the communication materials. The link are mainly for partners, who have the access to the SharePoint.

The document also reports the email address to contact for any additional questions regarding the use of the AMON logo and visual identity.

¹ Clean Hydrogen Partnership, Visual Identity Manual https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/media/visual-identity_en

Index

01. Concept page 3	02. Logo page 3	03. Pictogram page 3	04. Use of the Logo page 7	05. Color palette page 8
06. Construction lines page 8	07. Clearance space page 10	08. Color applications page 11	09. Typography of the Logo page 13	10. Minimum size page 13
11. Sample Images page 14	12. Infographics page 15	13. Applications page 16	14. Acknowledgement of EU funding page 18	
15. Partner Logos page 18	16. Report page 21	17. Presentation page 22	18. Branding of infrastructure page 23	

01. Concept

USE AND CONVERSION OF AMMONIA INTO HIGH EFFICIENCY ELECTRICITY WITH A SOLAR WIND FUEL CELL

- #start
- #molecule
- #transformation
- #cell
- #energy
- #future
- #simplicity

01. Concept

The logo is introduced by the 'M' molecule that locates itself on the 'a' part of the branding resulting a passage from one environment to another. Another statement is the symbol of the ignition 'ON' which is being a part of the main, emphasizing the narrative 'from ammonia to power'. The blue color represents air and water, and green represents green energy. The power symbolizes the project.

02. Logo

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

03. Pictogram

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

04. Use of the Logo

The logo and pictogram shall be used in its entirety without distorting, modifying or separating its component elements. The AMON logo shall be used by the firms to communicate, trade and work where AMON is presented. The logo of AMON may be used by the companies subject to the following terms and conditions:

Request for permission can be submitted to the Commercial Team by email: info@amonfc.com. It is not recommended to use logos that are not compatible with the aims and principles of the project.

Be cautious:
The height cannot be determined, the color and typography cannot be changed, do not use shading or just the outline, the angle cannot be changed.

05. Color palette

water, freedom, atmosphere

earth, chemical reaction, green energy

06. Construction lines

07. Clearance space

The production area of the logo is highly recommended to guarantee the visual integrity and/or an identification of the logo and project in the different applications.

08. Color applications

09. Typography of the Logo

LOGO TYPEFACE

Typo Round Bold

SECONDARY TYPEFACE

DOSIS

Aa Aa Aa Aa Aa

ABCDEF GHIKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 €@ 1234567890 *\$%&#

SUPPORT TYPEFACE (for text paragraph)

RUBIK

ABCDEF GHIKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 €@ 1234567890 *\$%&#

10. Minimum size

The minimum size for the logo should be respected to guarantee its readability.

The minimum width for the complete logo is 3cm.

The minimum width for the logo without the paragraph is 2cm.

The minimum width for the pictogram is 1cm.

11. Sample Images

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

11. Sample Images

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

12. Infographics

13. Applications

Possible applications for the communication toolkit including card, roll-up, branded cap.

14. Acknowledgement of EU funding

As a beneficiary of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, AMON has the legal obligation to acknowledge the EU funding received.

LINK DOWNLOAD

15. Logos of Partners

LINK DOWNLOAD

15. Logos of Partners

LINK DOWNLOAD

16. Report template

17. Presentation template

The templates should be used both for internal meetings and external events, where AMON is presented.

18. Branding of infrastructure

Any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major is suit funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership must acknowledge EU support and display the Partnership logo, European flag (optional) and funding statement (optional) into local languages, where appropriate. Production of any branding material (physically visible) is the sole responsibility of the beneficiary and is not supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

Typically all funding partners are acknowledged on each equipment. The Clean Hydrogen Partnership logo and the EU emblem shall be of the same size as other funding partners, unless circumstances should they be smaller than the logo of other funding partners. Next to the above, the logo of AMON should be located. The logos should be clearly visible and be adapted to the size of the equipment.

Minimum size for small applications: 30 x 50 cm.
Minimum size for large-scale applications: 60 x 60 cm.

Figure 7. Screenshot of AMON Branding Guidelines

04. Communication materials

In the first six months of the project, the visual identity has been used to produce most AMON communication materials, which will be then complemented by new documents when the results will be available and will require the creation of additional materials.

The materials created are:

1. The branding guidelines, already explained in chapter 03 of this report.
2. The basic infographic, which was used to create the 3D images of the technology and its applications.
3. A short video, which quickly show the AMON technology.
4. The library, which includes the above-mentioned images and other infographics created by the subcontractor.
5. The roll-up.
6. The flyer.

The communication toolkit (Deliverable D5.3) expected by December 2023 (M12) will describe the communication materials already prepared and the plans for additional materials.

The communication materials are available to partners and uploaded in the folder of the project repository and they can be downloaded by any partner.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the AMON repository

05. Project Website and Socials

5.1 Project Website

The project website has been designed by the subcontractor with the guidance and content provided by the Communication leader (FBK), approved by the Consortium. The website has been officially launched on the 22nd of June 2023 (M6). It already included three news about conferences where Partners have participated and presented the project, and two results.

As described in the precedent paragraphs, the webpage will be the public window where to showcase the state-of-art of the activities and results achieved. Therefore, it uses a user-friendly design, a simple structure, and a semi-technical language to describe and present the project AMON to multiple audiences: academic and professional stakeholders operating in the ammonia and hydrogen field, industries, policymakers, and European citizens.

A dedicated domain and hosting have been purchased to host the website until the end of the project (month 36) and then it will be renewed for additional five years after the official end of the project, as requested by the Horizon Europe programme.

The website is available at <https://www.amon-project.eu>

It will be periodically updated during the project lifetime with dedicated content to improve awareness and engagement of stakeholders.

The homepage "Project" contains a GIF (Graphics Interchange Format) of the AMON Technology and provides a summary description of the project ambition and objectives, and an overview of the consortium partners. On the main page there are also snapshots of the news.

Figure 9. AMON website - "Project"

From the home, a page can be opened where all partners are introduced also underlining the activities they will participate in or will be responsible for within the AMON project.

Figure 10. Consortium webpage

The “Prototype” page regards the technology that will be developed in AMON: each component is described in details and the innovative aspects of AMON are outlined.

Figure 11. AMON website - "Prototype"

The "Results" page is divided in three main sections, and it is the main repository of all publications, public deliverables, and other materials produced by the AMON project.

Figure 12. AMON Website "Results"

The "News" page collects all the news on the AMON activities, participation at events, conferences, etc., and main results.

Figure 13. AMON Website "News"

The website is structured in five pages accessible via a classic first-level menu. It was decided not to add second-level pages to ease navigation and help users find content in a simple and intuitive way. However, the website is a dynamic tool and, in case of need, dedicated subpages can be added. AMON contact of the Project Coordinator and Project Manager are provided at the bottom of each page.

5.2 Social Media Accounts

On the 6th of June 2023 (M6), the Communication Manager opened two social media accounts of AMON Project:

1. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/amon-project-eu/>
2. Twitter: <https://twitter.com/AmonProjectEU>

LinkedIn is a social network that is mainly preferred by professionals and business managers, but also liked by academic and research centers. Twitter communicates with short posts known as tweets and it is the favorite social tool by policymakers.

The two accounts will be used to promote all the news that will be published on the AMON website, as well as the news posted by Partners.

Figure 14. Screenshot of the social media account of AMON project

The image displays two overlapping social media profiles for 'AMON Project EU'. The background profile is on LinkedIn, showing the company name, 'Ammonia to Power', and a bio: 'Renewable Energy Power Generation · Trento, Trentino-Alto Adige · 12 followers'. The foreground profile is on Twitter, showing a tweet from June 6, 2023, with the text: 'AMON Project is officially on social media! We are excited to announce that we are creating a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into #electric #power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell system. ⚡💧'. The tweet includes a photo of a group of people and mentions several partners like @VTTFinland, DTU, and others.

06. Conclusions

This document describes the visual identity of the project AMON, the communication materials and the website that will be used for the dissemination and communication activities of the project.

Part of this report will also be included in the definition of the D&C Plan which will report the set of activities for targeting multiple stakeholders and achieving the D&C targets set in the Grant Agreement.

The visual identity will greatly contribute to guarantee the future exploitation of the AMON Key Exploitable Results, in line with the objectives set by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

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FONDAZIONE
BRUNO KESSLER
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(Italy)

SolydEra
(Italy)

Alfa Laval Technologies
AB (Sweden),
Alfa Laval Aalborg
AS (Denmark),
Alfa Laval SPA (Italy)

SAPIO
Produzione Idrogeno
Ossigeno Srl
(Italy)

KIWA Nederland
BV (The Netherlands)
e KIWA Cermet (Italy)

VTT Technical
Research Centre
of Finland
(Finland)

Technical University
of Denmark
(Denmark)

Ecole Polytechnique
Fédérale De Lausanne
(Switzerland)

Electrolyser &
Fuel Cell Forum
(Switzerland)

Fachhochschule Zentralschweiz
Hochschule Luzern
(Switzerland)

Amon – Ammonia to power

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Center for Sustainable Energy | FBK

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